

Qualitative Study on Adverse Effects of Social Vices on Sustainable Growth and Development in Nigeria: a Review

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Abstract

The article examined the adverse effects of social problems, the sustainable growth and development in Nigeria. It adopts systematic review research method, and several search engines such as google scholar, Google, Researchgate, among others, were used to search for materials of interest that cover between 2010 and 2023. In addition, content analysis was used to group materials into major themes, thereby subjecting them to thematic analysis towards addressing the objective of the study. The article revealed that, Nigeria is combated with several social problems which are poverty, unemployment, inflation, budget deficits, street begging, prostitution, frauds, high crime rates, terrorist insurgency, collapse of manufacturing industries, corruption in public service, lack of entrepreneurial development, among others. In addition, these social problems have affected several aspects of the nation's economy which include the individual, social, political, economic, and several other aspects of the economy. It has also led to life threatening events and the loss of lives and properties, and also affecting entrepreneurial growth and development in Nigeria, thereby hampering growth and development of the nation. It has also led to social disorganization, dysfunctions, deviation, among others in the Nigeria society. The study therefore recommends that social movement and groups should focus on ensuring that their campaigns focus on the implementation of the critical national economic, political, social, cultural, educational and health services.

Keywords: Social problems, Social problems in Nigeria, Effects of Social problems, Nigeria

Introduction

Social problems are becoming major issues in the society, and could include a wide range of issues such as poverty, unemployment, displacement, terrorism, drug abuse, crime, ageing, among others (Macionis, 2008). Unlike other issues such as natural disasters, social problems are created by society hence, they could be solved by the society (Vaghefi and Drew, 2023). A social problem could be referred to as conditions or behaviors that could pose negative consequences on large numbers of people in the society and could be generally recognized as one that needs to be addressed. According to Spector & Kitsuse (2001), social problems, often go through natural history, which consist of several stages of development. The different stages of social problems are the emergence and claims making, legitimacy, renewed claims making, and development of alternative strategies.

At the emergence and claims making, social problems arise when social entities such as individuals, social change group, news media, and influential politicians, among others begin to draw attention to particular issues that are perceived to be undesirable and are in dire need for remedy. During this process, it goes into the public thereby, influencing the public perceptions on that particular issue, articulating the problems, the reasons and also the possible solutions. However, many of such emergence and claims making efforts of social problems do not succeed hence, social problem may not be recognized or doesn't emerge but few may succeed by drawing public attention to certain problem hence, social problem has emerged.

After the first stage, the second stage is the legitimacy stage. At this second stage of legitimacy, it focuses on persuading the government which could be at the local, state, and/or federal, to take some action towards alleviating such social problems such as in spending, policy making, among others towards addressing the problem. After, the second stage came, the third stage of renewed claims making, which emphasized that even when the government takes necessary action, social change groups often emphasized that such actions could be limited to successfully addressing such social problem. Therefore, such groups often press their demands anew hence the renewed claims making which could involve a certain level of tension towards attaining their goals and objective.

After this stage, the fourth stage is the development of alternative strategies, which focuses on the development of own strategies for addressing the social problem, while waiting for the government to respond. This third stage is executed because social change groups are often of the opinion that the government and other established interests may not respond early or adequately to their claims hence, provide alternative strategies in tackling the issues pending the time when the government

responds. The movement from stage one to second and third stages is a function of the recognized and persuaded need for issues to be addressed. This is hinged on the three main characteristics of social problems provided by Vaghefi and Drew (2023), which are the reasons, negative effects and the social solution. The social reason is what is used to compel the society and the government that such issue is a social problem and that it needs to be addressed. The negative effect implies the negative impact it may pose on the society, thereby threatening life, safety, and freedom among others.

The third characteristic is the social solution, because every social problem should have social solution else, it is not a social problem (Vaghefi and Drew, 2023). Drawing emphasis from the three characteristics of social problem, understanding the social effect of a social problem is very germane in the emergence and claims making and legitimacy stage, and also at the renewed claims making, and development of alternative strategies towards providing better and sustainable solution to such social problems.

It is no doubt that social problems could pose several effects on the society. In Nigeria, several social issues that have affected the society are poverty, unemployment, terrorism, crime, kidnapping, cultism, drug abuse, among others (George & Ukpong, 2013). Also, the effects of social problems are grave and could cut across the individuals, family, society and the nation. For example, for individuals, it could lead to loss of lives, loss of reputation and dignity, unemployment, frustration, among others. For family, it could lead to broken home, poverty and low standard of living, among others. Also, for the nation, it could dent the nation's image at the global level, and also lead to loss of lives and properties, couple with loss of social amenities and resources. Moreover, there are several other effects that are needed to be understood to be able to drive social problems towards obtaining social solution in the Nigeria society. This article focuses on presenting the various social problems and their adverse effects on the sustainable growth and development in Nigeria.

Social problems are increasing and are becoming major issue that attract not only local attention but regional and global attention in Nigeria and cuts across crime, moral decadence, poverty, kidnapping, suicidal, murder, poor education, among others (Ogogo, 2023). According to Ogogo (2023), these social problems are posing significant effects on the economy, human existence, social and national development, and it is also negatively affecting development, which include sustainable development in the nation due to the high level of societal issues. In addition, this could pose negative effect on national strength and the pride of the nation (Ofoche, 2012; Ogogo, 2023). This could in the long run hinder the attainment of the sustainable development goals in Nigeria leading to failure in achieving SDGs. This could further affect future development of Nigeria and hence, unable to partake in future global development plans leading to under-development or setbacks in development at the regional and global levels.

Social problems in Nigeria have become a major issue of concern due to the high rate of several social issues battling the nation such as increasing rate of crime, moral decadence, poverty, kidnapping, suicidal, murder, poor education, among others (Ogogo, 2023). In addition, its elastic effects is felt on several aspects of the economy such as human existence, social and national development, couple with its jeopardizing effect on national strength and pride of the nation (Ogogo, 2023).

According to Ofoche (2012), religious crisis, political crisis, high rate of corruption, tribalism, poor education system, increase illiteracy rate, a huge gap between the wealthy and the poor, poor judiciary system, weak institution, increase in criminal networks, increasing unrest, among others are major social problems that are leading to a state of hopelessness, and affecting social economic status of individuals and the society in the nation. Juxtaposing the works of Ofoche (2012) and Ogogo (2023) together, it could be noted that there are several social problems in the Nigeria society, and all these have posed significant effect on the society, with regards to individual, economic, and the nation as a whole hence, could affect development of the nation.

Also, studies such as NISER (2000); UNDP (2006); Robinson and Anthony (2014) stated that several cases of social problems in Nigeria are increasing hunger, inflation, budget deficits, debt overhang, street begging, prostitution, frauds, high crime rates in major cities, terrorist insurgency, poverty, youth unemployment, collapse of manufacturing industries, corruption in public service, stagnation in entrepreneurial development, among others. These have hunted and affected Nigeria efforts for development since independence where virtually all notions and models of development have been experimented but to no avail (Aremu, 2003; Robinson and Anthony, 2014).

According to Hakizimana (2017), social problems could lead to social disorganization, dysfunctions, deviation, among others. Social disorganization implies human activities or failures which act or tend to impede other social activities. Social dysfunctions are socially related activities which tend to counter or disrupt the institutional nexus, or frustrate individual or social needs. Social deviation implies deviating from the normal behavior in the society and could encompass issues such as crime, delinquency, drug addiction, prostitution, physical handicaps, among others.

Juxtaposing the works of NISER (2000); UNDP (2006); Ofoche (2012); Robinson and Anthony (2014), Hakizimana (2017); and Ogogo (2023), it could be affirmed that social problems could lead to several social related issues in the Nigeria society such as social disorganization, dysfunctions, and deviation, and also lack of entrepreneurial development. This could hamper the development of the individuals, society and the nation. This implies that the effect of social problems move from the individual level to the society and then to national level hence, affecting the sustainable growth and development of the nation in the long run.

Methodology

The article deploys a systematic review method to achieve its objectives. Therefore, the Information and materials used in this article were obtained from journal articles, books, and other similar materials, including online materials that tend to focus on the major objective of this study. In addition, information and materials selected focused on year range between 2010 and 2023 so as to obtain more recent information that meet the aims of the study. Also, the study uses [Cochrane reviews](#) style of reviewing literature by Chapman (2014), particularly in the searching process to obtain useful materials that are used in the study. This also follows the use of PICOS, representing (Richardson, 1995):

P – Problem or Population

I – Intervention

C – Control or comparator

O – Outcome(s)

S - Study type (e.g. quantitative, qualitative, etc.)

Also, search engine used for this systematic review are google, google scholar and other search engines, yielding several results and outcomes but very few (only seven articles) were selected that were fit and used for this study, towards meeting the goal of the study. Moreover, the information and materials were subjected to thematic analysis where they are grouped into various themes of the objectives and content analysis was also used to analyse the information resources obtained towards addressing the objective of the study.

Results

The result section focuses on providing responses to understanding of the effects of social problems to the peace of Nigeria. According to [StopLearn Team](#) (2023), social problems effects could be divided into several aspects of the society. For example, some social problems affecting individuals in Nigeria are:

1. Sexual immorality and wide range of sexually transmitted diseases: the rate of increasing varieties of sexually transmitted diseases (STD) such as syphilis, gonorrhoea, herpes, staphylococcus, HIV/AIDS, among others have been the result of the noisome sexual immorality battling the nation. It has also resulted in high rate of unwanted pregnancies, school dropout and truncation of education career, leading to early or unplanned marriage, single parenthood, thereby constituting major issues to families and the society at large.
2. Poverty: The rate of poverty in Nigeria is alarming, and couple with the high rate of unemployment, and also high cost of living. Poverty could also lead to several other social issues such as malnutrition, sicknesses, and diseases among others. It has also led to street begging as provided by Ogogo (2023) in Figure 1. In addition, it has also led to school dropout, children becoming street children, miscreants, area boys, prostitutes, and robbers among others. Also, according to Omiunu (2017), an average of 70% and an approximately 24% of Nigerians are poor and unemployed respectively hence, families are incapacitated in various ways to cater for themselves in the society.

Figure 1: Street begging as a result of high rate of Poverty

Source: Ogogo (2023)

3. Crimes: There is also high rate of crimes in the Nigeria society, and this has also led to increasing rate of [insecurity](#) to individual lives, properties and the society. Also, others affecting families in Nigeria include ([StopLearn Team, 2023](#)):
4. Conflict: there are several other problems in the society such as poverty, unemployment, inequality, religious issues, among others that have increased the rate of conflicts in the Nigeria society. These have affected the peace of people, society, and family among others. Examples of such conflicts are provided in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Inter-ethnic tension between Yoruba and Hausa in Southwest, Nigeria ([Animasawun](#), 2016).

5. Indiscipline and Disobedience in the Family: Indiscipline and disrespect to the authority such as parents, community elders, among others are increasing in the Nigeria society. Children are found to be disobedience to parents, teachers, community leaders, among others, and this has caused several issues of interest in the Nigeria society.
6. Child abuse: Due to the increasing rate of poverty and unemployment, children are seen engaged in street hawking, thereby exposing these children to various forms of evil such as kidnapping, raping, promiscuity, truancy, among others.
7. High Cost of Living: Also, due to high cost of living, several families in Nigeria are struggling to make ends meet, and to be able to provide for the family, but to no avail. This has also constituted several issues of concerns in the Nigeria society.
8. In addition, social problems affecting the nation of Nigeria are ([StopLearn Team](#), 2023):
9. Political instability: The increasing rate of electoral fraud, social injustice, among others have led to political instability in Nigeria, and this has jeopardize the society, posing negative effect to the political economy and the society at large.
10. Social instability: Social instability, which refers to the breakdown of law and order in society, is very much prevalence in Nigeria and has led to high level of [insecurity](#) of lives, properties and families.
11. Militancy: The high rate of perceived socio-economic injustice in Nigeria to certain groups of the nation has led to high rate of Militancy, particularly in the oil producing Niger Delta region where the youths take up arms against the establishment and the government. Also, there is the terrorist group, such as “Boko-Haram” (an Islamic Sect) bombing and destroying lives and property in some parts of Nigeria through suicide missions claiming that Western Education is a sin. This is another arm of political and religious instability or issue of the nation. An example of the clash of militants is presented in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3: Clash of Militants (Felbab-Brown, 2020)

12. Economic depression: Problems such as corruption, inefficiency, greed, and selfishness are increasing seriously and have led to economic depression in Nigeria where individuals, families and the society are really suffering from basic facilities and amenities such as pipe borne water, electricity, health system, among others leading to several effects on the society
13. Disunity: religious and ethnicity disunity are also social problems that have drawn several attention in the Nigeria society, hence, affecting the peace of the nation through ethnic and religious violence especially in the northern part of the nation.
14. Studies also revealed that social problems could affect the political and economic stability of a nation, loss of valuable man power, threats on lives and properties, leading to the lack of development, increasing mental health issues, and also general disorder (Ogogo, 2023). According to George and Ukpong (2013), social problems could pose tremendous effect on national growth and development of Nigeria. Also, Oludele (2020) revealed that several social problems such as corruption, declining quality of education, family problems (such as increased divorce and family abuse/struggle), gender discrimination, governmental abuse of power, poverty, racial discrimination, among others are posing several effects on human, and socio-economic development of the nation. Also, Ucha (2010) noted that poverty, as a social problem has also led to poor health, lack of basic health amenities and competent medical practitioners, increasing rate of children with physical defects due to the inability of their parents to take them for immunization. Also, Aver, Nnorom and Targba (2013) noted that social problems such as violence could affect social development which has affected several aspects of the Nigeria economy such as ethics, nations, religions and tribes.

Discussion of Findings

The article examined the social problems and its adverse effects on the sustainable growth and development in Nigeria. The findings revealed that social problems are very many in Nigeria and has affected several aspect of the nation's economy which include the individual, social, political, economic, and several other aspects of the economy. It has also led to life threatening events and the loss of lives and properties, and also affecting entrepreneurial growth and development in Nigeria, thereby hampering growth and development of the nation. This supports the works of Spector & Kitsuse (2001); Macionis (2008); Ofoche (2012); George & Ukpong (2013); Robinson and Anthony (2014); Hakizimana (2017); Vaghefi and Drew (2023); Ogogo (2023); among others that there are several social related problems in Nigeria and these are posing elastic effect on personal, social, economic, religious development hence, leading to social disorganization, dysfunctions, deviation, among others in the Nigeria society. This could hamper development and development effort in Nigeria thereby leading to underdevelopment in the short and long run. In addition, the findings of this study concur with those of Aremu (2003) and Robinson and Anthony (2014), that these elastic social problems have hunted and affected Nigeria for long since independence and has affected virtually all efforts and models of development which have proven abortive, without solution.

Conclusion

The article examined the social problems and its adverse effects on the sustainable growth and development in Nigeria. In conclusion, Nigeria is combated with several social problems which are poverty, unemployment, inflation, budget deficits, street begging, prostitution, frauds, high crime rates, terrorist insurgency, collapse of manufacturing industries, corruption in public service, lack of entrepreneurial development, among others. In addition, these social problems have affected several aspects of the nation's economy which include the individual, social, political, economic, and several other aspects of the economy hence, on the sustainable growth and development of the nation. It has also led to life threatening events and the loss of lives and properties, and also affecting entrepreneurial growth and development in Nigeria, thereby hampering growth and development of the nation. It has also led to social disorganization, dysfunctions, deviation, among others in the Nigeria society.

Recommendations

The study therefore recommends that:

1. Social movement and groups should focus on ensuring that their campaigns focus on the implementation of the critical national economic, political, social, cultural, educational and health services.
2. Political parties should also evolve as mechanism of democratic governance rather than looting the nation's wealth and using the society to generate wealth for their selfish gains,
3. Government and policy makers should also endeavour to focus on meeting and solving germane issues of the society that relate to social problems and give attention to them towards ameliorating these social problems in the society.

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